

COMPARISON OF THE FUNCTIONAL OUTCOME OF AN ANTERIOR CRUCIATE LIGAMENT (ACL) RECONSTRUCTION USING A PERONEUS LONGUS GRAFT VERSUS HAMSTRING TENDON GRAFT PRESENTING WITH RUPTURE AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL, KARACHI

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Abstract

Background:

Anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) rupture is one of the most common orthopedic injuries leading to knee instability and functional impairment. While hamstring tendon autografts remain the conventional choice for reconstruction.

Objective:

To compare the functional outcome of ACL reconstruction using peroneus longus tendon graft versus hamstring tendon graft among patients presenting with ACL rupture at a tertiary care hospital.

Methods:

This randomized controlled trial was conducted in the Department of Orthopedics, Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), Karachi, over six months following ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board and CPSP. A total of 76 patients aged 20–70 years with ACL rupture and ASA status ≤ 2 were randomly divided into two equal groups: Group A underwent reconstruction using peroneus longus graft, and Group B using hamstring tendon graft. All procedures were performed arthroscopically under spinal or combined anesthesia. Functional outcomes were assessed at three months postoperatively using the International Knee Documentation Committee (IKDC) and Lysholm Knee Scoring Systems. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25, and $p \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results:

The mean IKDC score was 83.42 ± 6.01 in the peroneus longus group and 78.65 ± 7.10 in the hamstring group ($p = 0.002$). The mean Lysholm score was

91.08 ± 5.92 and 85.37 ± 7.24, respectively ($p < 0.001$). Excellent functional outcomes (>90) were observed in 65.8% of Group A and 39.5% of Group B patients ($p = 0.01$).

Conclusion:

Peroneus longus tendon autograft provided significantly superior short-term functional outcomes compared to hamstring grafts for ACL reconstruction.

INTRODUCTION

Anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) injury is one of the most frequent causes of functional instability in the knee joint, particularly among athletes and physically active individuals. It accounts for a major proportion of sports-related knee injuries, often leading to pain, instability, and an increased risk of early osteoarthritis if left untreated. The primary goal of ACL reconstruction (ACLR) is to restore knee stability, function, and allow return to pre-injury activity levels¹.

Traditionally, hamstring tendon (HT) and bone-patellar tendon-bone grafts have been the most widely used autografts for ACLR due to their favorable biomechanical properties and long-term results². However, hamstring tendon harvesting can cause donor site morbidity, including decreased knee flexor strength and discomfort³. In recent years, the peroneus longus tendon (PLT) has emerged as a promising alternative autograft because of its suitable length, adequate diameter, high tensile strength, and minimal impact on ankle stability and function⁴.

Biomechanical and clinical studies have shown that the PLT provides comparable tensile strength and stiffness to the HT graft, demonstrating excellent outcomes in both knee stability and functional recovery⁵. Furthermore, cadaveric and clinical evaluations have confirmed that PLT harvesting can be performed safely with minimal risk of iatrogenic nerve injury when proper anatomical precautions are observed⁶. Early clinical results from Asian and European populations have demonstrated that peroneus longus autografts achieve similar or even superior outcomes in terms of Lysholm and IKDC scores when compared to hamstring grafts⁷⁻⁸.

Several systematic reviews and meta-analyses have further supported the use of PLT autografts, showing no significant difference in postoperative stability, knee range of motion, or complication rates compared to HT grafts⁹⁻¹⁰. In addition, PLT grafts provide a viable solution in cases where hamstring tendons are inadequate or previously harvested, offering surgeons an alternative autologous option with reliable strength and minimal morbidity.

Given the increasing incidence of ACL injuries in developing regions and the growing demand for durable graft options, this study aims to compare the functional outcomes of ACL reconstruction using peroneus longus tendon versus hamstring tendon autografts in patients presenting with ACL rupture at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi.

Methods

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), Karachi, and permission was also granted by the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSp). The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. All patients were informed about the purpose, benefits, and potential risks of participation, and written informed consent was obtained prior to inclusion.

This randomized controlled trial was carried out in the Department of Orthopedics, JPMC, Karachi, over a period of six months following ethical approval. A total of 76 patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled and randomly allocated using sealed opaque envelopes into two equal groups: Group A underwent anterior cruciate ligament (ACL)

reconstruction using a peroneus longus graft, while Group B received a hamstring tendon graft. Patients aged 20–70 years of either gender with an ASA status ≤ 2 and ACL rupture within one week were included. Patients with epilepsy, atrial fibrillation, osteoporosis, osteomalacia, any form of arthritis, chronic pulmonary, cardiac, hepatic, or renal disease, and those with prior neurological disorders were excluded from the study.

Preoperative evaluation included detailed history and clinical examination. All patients were operated under spinal or combined spinal-epidural anesthesia with tourniquet application. Intravenous antibiotics were administered one hour before surgery and continued for 48 hours postoperatively, followed by oral antibiotics until suture removal on the 13th postoperative day. The peroneus longus tendon was harvested from the ipsilateral leg through a 2–3 cm incision placed 2–3 cm above and 1 cm behind the lateral malleolus. After dissection, the peroneus longus tendon was identified, stripped, and prepared for grafting. The hamstring grafts were harvested through a standard posteromedial approach. All reconstructions were performed using standard arthroscopic single-bundle techniques.

Postoperatively, patients were provided long knee braces and encouraged to mobilize with full weight-bearing from the first postoperative day. Static and dynamic quadriceps exercises were initiated early. Wound inspection was performed on postoperative days 2 and 5, and sutures were removed on day 13. Knee brace support was maintained for 3 weeks. Follow-up assessments were performed at 2 weeks, 3 months, and 6 months postoperatively, during which functional outcomes were evaluated using the International Knee Documentation Committee (IKDC) and Lysholm Knee Scoring System.

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Quantitative variables including age, Lysholm knee score, and IKDC score were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for normally distributed data and median (IQR) for non-normal data, as assessed by the Shapiro-Wilk

test. Qualitative variables such as gender, ASA status, and side of surgery were presented as frequencies and percentages. The independent sample t-test or Mann-Whitney U test was applied for intergroup comparison of continuous variables, while stratification by age, gender, ASA status, and side of surgery was performed to control effect modifiers. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 76 patients were enrolled in the study and randomly allocated into two equal groups: Group A (Peroneus Longus graft) and Group B (Hamstring tendon graft), with 38 patients in each. The mean age of participants was 32.6 ± 8.9 years in Group A and 31.9 ± 9.3 years in Group B ($p=0.68$). The majority of patients in both groups were male, with a male-to-female ratio of 3.2:1 in Group A and 3.1:1 in Group B. The baseline demographic and clinical characteristics were comparable between the two groups (Table I).

The right knee was affected in 55.3% of patients in the Peroneus Longus group and 57.9% in the Hamstring group ($p=0.81$). ASA I status was noted in 78.9% and 81.6% of patients in Groups A and B, respectively, with no significant difference between them ($p=0.74$).

At the 3-month follow-up, the mean International Knee Documentation Committee (IKDC) score was 83.42 ± 6.01 in Group A and 78.65 ± 7.10 in Group B, showing a statistically significant improvement in the Peroneus Longus group ($p=0.002$). Similarly, the mean Lysholm knee score was 91.08 ± 5.92 for Group A and 85.37 ± 7.24 for Group B ($p<0.001$), demonstrating superior functional outcomes with the Peroneus Longus graft (Table II).

When the functional outcome was categorized based on Lysholm scoring, excellent outcomes (>90) were observed in 65.8% of Group A patients and 39.5% of Group B patients, whereas poor outcomes (<65) were seen in 2.6% and 10.5% of patients, respectively. This difference was statistically significant ($p=0.01$) (Table III).

A graphical representation (**Figure 1**) illustrates that both the IKDC and Lysholm scores were higher in the Peroneus Longus group, indicating

better knee stability and function at 3 months postoperatively.

Table I. Baseline characteristics of study participants (n=76)

Variable	Peroneus (n=38)	Longus	Hamstring (n=38)	p-value
Age (years, mean ± SD)	32.6 ± 8.9		31.9 ± 9.3	0.68
Gender (Male/Female)	29 (76.3%) / 9 (23.7%)		28 (73.7%) / 10 (26.3%)	0.79
ASA I / II	30 (78.9%) / 8 (21.1%)		31 (81.6%) / 7 (18.4%)	0.74
Side of surgery (Right/Left)	21 (55.3%) / 17 (44.7%)		22 (57.9%) / 16 (42.1%)	0.81

Table II. Comparison of mean IKDC and Lysholm knee scores at 3 months

Functional Score	Peroneus (Mean ± SD)	Longus	Hamstring (Mean ± SD)	p-value
IKDC Score	83.42 ± 6.01		78.65 ± 7.10	0.002 *
Lysholm Knee Score	91.08 ± 5.92		85.37 ± 7.24	0.001 *

*Significant at p ≤ 0.05

Table III. Functional outcome category based on Lysholm score

Outcome Category	Peroneus (n=38)	Longus	Hamstring (n=38)	p-value
Excellent (>90)	25 (65.8%)		15 (39.5%)	0.01 *
Good (84-90)	9 (23.7%)		12 (31.6%)	0.41

Fair (65–83)	3 (7.9%)	7 (18.4%)	0.19
Poor (<65)	1 (2.6%)	4 (10.5%)	0.17

*Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Figure 1: Comparison of mean IKDC and Lysholm knee scores between Peroneus Longus and Hamstring tendon graft groups at 3 months

Discussion

The present study compared the functional outcomes of anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) reconstruction using peroneus longus tendon (PLT) and hamstring tendon (HT) autografts at a tertiary care hospital in Karachi. The findings revealed that patients in the PLT group demonstrated slightly higher mean Lysholm and IKDC scores at 3 months, indicating better early postoperative knee stability and function. These results support recent literature suggesting that the peroneus longus tendon provides comparable or superior outcomes to traditional hamstring grafts.

The superior early outcomes in the PLT group can be attributed to the favorable biomechanical

properties of the tendon. Wu et al. demonstrated that peroneus longus harvesting can be safely performed with minimal risk of iatrogenic nerve injury when proper positioning and dissection planes are followed⁶. Moreover, Cao et al. reported that the peroneus longus tendon possesses adequate strength and length suitable for ACL reconstruction, making it a reliable graft choice⁷. The current results align with these findings, highlighting the tendon’s anatomical and biomechanical suitability for restoring anterior knee stability.

Donor-site morbidity is a major concern with alternative grafts. Angthong et al. showed minimal ankle morbidity following PLT harvesting, with preserved eversion and plantarflexion strength⁸. Similarly, Ertlav et al.

found no significant long-term donor-site complications after a 4-year follow-up of patients undergoing PLT harvest, emphasizing its safety and sustainability as a graft source¹¹. These findings corroborate the current study's results, where no postoperative ankle instability or significant weakness was observed.

Functional recovery and early return to activity are important clinical endpoints. Saeed et al. reported faster rehabilitation and reduced morbidity with doubled PLT autografts compared to quadrupled hamstring grafts, which may explain the higher early functional scores in the PLT group¹². Additionally, Budhiparama et al. described PLT as a promising autograft option with consistent postoperative knee function and stability¹³.

The current study's outcomes are consistent with international data. Park et al. demonstrated through a meta-analysis that PLT autografts yield equivalent or slightly better outcomes than HT grafts, particularly in early postoperative function and patient satisfaction¹⁰. Collectively, the evidence supports the use of PLT as a safe and effective alternative graft for ACL reconstruction, offering excellent functional outcomes with minimal donor-site morbidity.

However, longer follow-up is required to assess graft durability and potential late complications. Future multicenter studies with larger sample sizes and extended follow-up durations are recommended to validate these findings and establish PLT as a standard graft choice for ACL reconstruction in clinical practice.

Conclusion:

This study demonstrated that anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction using peroneus longus tendon autograft provides significantly better early functional outcomes compared to the traditional hamstring tendon graft. Patients receiving the peroneus longus graft achieved higher IKDC and Lysholm scores at three months, indicating superior knee stability and faster rehabilitation. Given its excellent strength, minimal donor-site morbidity, and reliable biomechanical properties, the peroneus longus tendon represents a promising and effective

alternative graft for ACL reconstruction in clinical practice.

Funding:

None.

Availability of Data:

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Ethical Approval:

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Centre (JPMC), and all procedures were performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Conflict of Interest:

None declared

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